

Original Research Article

Curing cancer while remembering the heart- a compelling case for all clinicians

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Abstract

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Oncology and Cardiology are two distinct medical worlds which just begin to collide. Given the early detection and improved intervention, more people than ever are surviving cancer. In Europe alone, there are 30 million cancer survivors, who are likely to develop some of the long-term side effects of chemotherapy, radiotherapy, and biological therapy (Lyon, 2019). This calls for clinicians of all sorts to adopt a new perspective when it comes to cancer patients and survivors. Cardio-Oncology is an exciting and rapidly evolving field in which Cardiology and Oncology are brought together. What Cardio-Oncology promises is a better quality of life for cancer survivors in terms of cardiovascular diseases and a chance for some patients to undergo the potentially life-saving cancer therapy. Since Cardio-Oncology also addresses the issue of early detection of subclinical and clinical cardiovascular conditions, the time has come for all clinicians and especially internists to learn how to approach cancer patients/survivors and to better understand the needs of this particular population.

Keywords: Atrial fibrillation, Biological therapy, Cancer, Cardio-oncology, Chemotherapy, Myocardial dysfunction, Quality of life

INTRODUCTION

Malignancies are a growing global concern, with an estimated 18.1 million new cases every year (WHO 2019). Despite the development of numerous state of the art therapies, 9.6 million people lose the battle with cancer early, making cancer the second leading cause of death (WHO 2019). However, more people are being cured of cancer than ever before, meaning that they will live long enough to experience the side effects of chemotherapy, radiotherapy, and biological therapy or even develop a second malignancy. Dealing with cancer survivors and their potential complications in the long term is somewhat new to clinicians, leaving many questions unanswered. Since cardiovascular diseases constitute the leading cause of mortality and a major contributor to the reduced quality of life, it is only natural to think of the cardiovascular risk of cancer patients and cancer survivors and if they should be considered a high-

risk population (ESC, 2016). Cardiovascular risk factors can be identified in the majority of patients and all clinicians, regardless of their medical specialty, should screen their patients in order to assess their risk of cardiovascular events. Since cancer patients and cancer survivors are likely to experience cancer therapy side effects and are more likely to develop other diseases (cancer-related or not), it is highly probable that they will be seen by clinicians from different specialties, not just oncologists. Hence, the principles of Cardio-Oncology should be understood by all of us, because at one point or another we could be the ones making a difference in the quality of life of these patients. Last but not least, although Cardio-Oncology provides us answers on how we can improve the quality of life in cancer patients, it in fact plays a vital role for a considerable amount of patients who are deemed unfit for chemotherapy or

biologic therapy because of their cardiovascular risk factors. In these particular cases, Cardio-Oncology is the ticket to a potentially life-saving therapy and clinicians should know how to select the cases in which the intervention of the specialist is beneficial. Therefore, Cardio-Oncology addresses not only the quality of life of cancer patients, but also their life expectancy.

METHODOLOGY AND AIM

We systematically reviewed the current literature regarding the subject in order to present what we considered to be the most relevant and important aspects in Cardio-Oncology. This review will address the issues of cardiac dysfunction and arrhythmias, especially atrial fibrillation, since they are more common in cancer patients than other matched populations and they are often underestimated by clinicians (Yeh et al., 2009). The thromboembolic disease is a common and potentially life-threatening complication and deserves to be discussed thoroughly in a dedicated review.

What is Cardio-Oncology?

Cardio-Oncology aims at understanding the cardiovascular side effects of cancer therapies and identifying the suitable cardiovascular approach in cancer patients. When thinking about Cardio-Oncology and cardiotoxicity, most clinicians consider only the cardiotoxicity of anthracyclines. Cardiotoxicity should be seen as an umbrella for a broader spectrum of cardiovascular diseases secondary to radiotherapy (RIHD-radiation-induced heart disease: valvular damage- stenosis and/or regurgitation, carotid stenosis, coronary artery disease, pericardial disease), chemotherapy (pericardial disease, left ventricle systolic/diastolic dysfunction) or biological therapy (especially, for the moment, *Trastuzumab*) (ESC, 2016). The *ESC Position Statement on Cardio-Oncology* defines the “9 Pillars of Cardio-Oncology” as the following clinical entities: myocardial dysfunction and heart failure, coronary artery disease, valvular heart disease, arrhythmias, arterial hypertension, thromboembolic disease, peripheral vascular disease and stroke, pulmonary hypertension and pericardial complications (Yeh et al, 2009).

Myocardial toxicity and cardiac dysfunction

The *American Society of Echocardiography (ASE)* and the *European Association of Cardiovascular Imaging (EACVI)* define the term of cancer therapeutics-related cardiac dysfunction as a decrease in left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) greater than 10 percentage points, to a value less than 53% (normal reference value

for 2D echocardiography) (ESC, 2016). There are two distinct types of cancer therapeutics-related cardiac dysfunction (CTRCD). Type I CTRCD is dose-dependent and is caused by anthracyclines such as doxorubicin, epirubicin, idarubicin, and mitoxantrone (ESC, 2016). They induce the formation of ternary complexes (topoisomerase-anthracycline-deoxyribonucleic acid) which will generate defective mitochondrial biogenesis and reactive oxygen species, which will eventually lead to myofibrillar disarray and cell death. Interestingly enough, although on a cellular level the damage is irreversible, cardiac function may be preserved or compensated through pharmacologic therapy (Yeh et al, 2009). Type II CTRCD is more recently described in patients receiving trastuzumab (primarily indicated for HER2-positive breast cancer (Yet et al, 2009). It is not dose-dependent and no ultrastructural abnormalities have been observed so far (Yeh et al, 2009). Therefore, unlike type I CTRCD, the damage is reversible (2-4 months after an interruption) and more importantly, rechallenging is considered safe since it does not carry the probability of recurrent and progressive cardiac dysfunction (Yeh et al, 2009). However, other agents are also included in type II CTRCD, such as sunitinib, sorafenib (non-selective tyrosine kinase inhibitors which affect “off-target” kinases from the heart and vasculature), bevacizumab, and more recently, ICI (immune checkpoint inhibitors) (Yeh et al, 2009). In practice, cancer patients are likely to be treated with more than one therapeutic agent, with type I and type II agents given sequentially or concurrently. Taking this into account, overlapping two types of cancer agents may result in cell death at the time of administration and unpredictable damage. Regarding radiotherapy, the risk for cardiac toxicity, marked interstitial myocardial fibrosis, valvular heart disease, and even coronary artery disease is greater in patients receiving concomitant chemotherapy (synergistic effect) and when the heart is near the site of irradiation (left breast, left lung and mediastinum) (ESC, 2016).

The most common cardiac side effect of cancer therapeutics is cardiac dysfunction, defined as previously described (ESC, 2016). However, reduced LVEF appears only in the late stages of myocardial toxicity. For this reason, the Royal Brompton Hospital Cardio-Oncology Clinic elaborated a classification of CTRCD by correlating cardiac biomarkers (brain natriuretic peptide - BNP), ultrasound parameters (diastolic function: E/E', systolic function: global longitudinal strain- GLS and LVEF) and symptoms (table 1) (Lyon, 2019). GLS is an ultrasound parameter which assesses the ratio between the shortening of the myocardial fibers in systole and their diastolic length and is computed using special software. Its normal values are intervendedor-variable, but in healthy subjects, GLS is around -20 (+/- 3), values greater than -16 are considered abnormal (Yeh et al, 2009). It is important to remember that although a decrease of more than 10 percentage points below LLN in LVEF suggests

Table 1. Adapted from the “ Royal Brompton Hospital Classification of Cancer Therapy-induced Myocardial Toxicity”; Pareek et al, *Eur J Heart Fail.* 2018 Dec; 20(12): 1721-1731.

Group	Classification	Definition	Biomarkers	E/E'>12 or GLS> -18%	LVEF reduction	Symptoms
1	Early biochemical cardiotoxicity	New BNP or Troponin I rise, but with normal cardiac imaging	+	-	-	-
2	Early functional cardiotoxicity	New reduction in GLS or grade III-IV diastolic dysfunction, normal biomarkers	-	+	-	-
3	Early mixed cardiotoxicity	Normal LVEF, but abnormal biomarkers, GLS↓/ diastolic dysfunction	+	+	-	-
4	HFpEF	Symptomatic heart failure with preserved ejection fraction	+	+	-	+
5	Asymptomatic LVSD	New LVEF reduction to <50% OR a reduction of >10% to a LVEF < 55%	+/-	+	+	-
6	HFrEF	Symptomatic reduction in LVEF < 50% or a reduction of >10% to a LVEF <55%	+	+	+	+

BNP: Brain Natriuretic Peptide; LVEF: left ventricular ejection fraction, HFpEF: heart failure with preserved ejection fraction; HFrEF: heart failure with reduce ejection fraction; LVSD: Left ventricular systolic dysfunction

cardiotoxicity, a reduction of more than 15% in global longitudinal strain (GLS) compared to the baseline suggests the risk of cardiotoxicity (ESC, 2016). Therefore, GLS is recommended as a means to follow patients at risk of cancer chemotherapy-related LV systolic dysfunction (ESC, 2016). The EACVI recommends an integrated approach to the correlation of global longitudinal strain and biomarkers (rise of the hs-troponin level after chemotherapy) (ESC, 2016). This provides incremental value in predicting subsequent CTRCD and the early detection of cardiac toxicity, especially in patients receiving anthracyclines and/or trastuzumab (still unclear for targeted molecular therapies) (Yeh et al, 2009). Even more, a rise in troponins identifies among the patients receiving anthracyclines those who may benefit from angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (ACE-Is) (ESC, 2016). In contrast to troponins, serum concentrations of natriuretic peptides, although reflecting elevated filling pressures, maybe less consistent in the early identification of CTRCD (ESC, 2016). Their role in identifying high-risk patients in the context of chemotherapy is not yet established, but they remain useful in the detection and surveillance of heart failure. (Table 1)

The classification is of particular importance for a couple of reasons. Firstly, it highlights the fact that CTRCD is a spectrum made up of different stages, ranging from early biochemical cardiotoxicity (when on BNP or Troponin I have abnormal values) to overt heart failure and identifies a pool of at-risk asymptomatic patients who otherwise would have been overlooked.

Furthermore, because of its synthetic nature, it can be easily used by any clinician and in any circumstance to identify cancer patients with subclinical forms of CTRCD or clinically manifesting CTRCD and also to assess their evolution. The optimal therapeutical strategy for each group is not well established and needs to be considered on an individual basis. However, for asymptomatic patients with LVSD (group 5), ACE-Is or ARBs combined with beta-blockers are recommended since they will improve the cardiac outcome, especially in the case of type I CTRCD (ESC, 2016).

Rhythm disturbances in the context of cancer patients

Up to 36% of cancer patients and survivors will experience cardiac arrhythmias and conduction defects (Farmakis et al, 2014). Some of the arrhythmias may be uneventful, but more often than in the general population they can induce severe symptoms or be life-threatening. Table 2 offers a synthetic review of the main rhythm disturbances and their relation to cancer therapeutics. Of note is that radiotherapy may induce sinus node dysfunction and conduction defects which are frequently permanent and require permanent cardiac stimulation (ESC, 2016). Because of their high prevalence and underestimated impact on cardiovascular prognosis, life quality, and mortality, we will focus on atrial fibrillation (AF) AF is the most common supraventricular arrhythmia in cancer patients and it can appear anytime : in patients

Table 2. Cancer drug agents associated with cardiac arrhythmias – Adapted from 2016 ESC Position on cancer treatments and cardiovascular toxicity, Eur Heart J (2016) 37, 2769-201

Type of arrhythmia	Causative drug
Bradycardia	Arsenic trioxide, bortezomib, capecitabine, cisplatin, cyclophosphamide, doxorubicine, epirubicine, 5-florouracil, ifosfamide, IL-2, methotrexate, mitoxantrone, paclitaxel, rituximab, thalidomide
Sinus tachycardia	Anthracyclines, carmustine
Atrioventricular block	Anthracyclines, arsenic trioxide, bortezomib, cyclophosphamide, 5-florouracil, mitoxantrone, rituximab, taxanes, thalidomide
Conduction disturbances	Anthracyclines, cisplatin, 5-florouracil, imatinib, taxanes
Atrial fibrillation	Alkylating agents, anthracyclines, capecitabine, 5-florouracil, gemcitabine, IL-2, interferons, rituximab, romidepsin, ponatinib, sorafenib, sunitinib, ibrutinib, amsacrine, etoposide, taxanes, vinca alkaloids
Supraventricular tachycardias	Alkylating agents, amsacrine, anthracyclines, capecitabine, 5-florouracil, methotrexate, bortezomib, doxorubicin, IL-2, interferons, paclitaxel, ponatinib, romidepsin
Ventricular tachycardia/fibrillation	Alkylating agents, amsacrine, capecitabine, 5-florouracil, gemcitabine, arsenic trioxide, doxorubicin, interferons, IL-2, methotrexate, paclitaxel, proteasome inhibitors (bortezomib, carfilzomib), rituximab, romidepsin
Sudden cardiac death	Anthracyclines- very rare, arsenic trioxide- secondary to torsade de pointes, 5-florouracil-related to ischaemia or coronary spasm, interferons, nilotinib, romidepsin.

Figure 1 : AF, heart failure (HF) and cancer patients.

with cancer, before treatment, due to direct tumor effect, during cancer treatment, or after cancer treatment. (Table 2)

However, the most common form of cancer-related AF is post-operative AF, particularly in patients undergoing lung resection (up to 18%) (Cardinale et al, 2007). In this particular case, a rise in NT-proBNP 1 hour after surgery accurately predicts AF (Ganatra et al, 2018). When addressing the issue of AF it is important to remember its multifaceted relation with heart failure, as illustrated

below (Figure 1). In the case of cancer patients, the relation is even more complex given that AF is a complication of many cancer therapeutics (see table 2) and many cancer patients will likely have an already impaired diastolic and/or systolic function. It is well established that AF is more common in cancer patients (more frequently: lung cancer, esophageal cancer, Hodgkin's lymphoma, leukemia, and in TSH suppressed patients for thyroid cancers than the respective matched populations) and some studies suggest that AF is an

independent risk factor for increased mortality in hospitalized patients with cancer (Cardinale et al, 2007).

The risk for incident AF in patients with cancer is highest in the first year after diagnosis (particularly in the first 3 months), even 4 times higher than in the general population, and decreases afterward (Cardinale et al, 2007) (ESC, 2016). Furthermore, up to 17% of patients receiving ibrutinib, currently used in Chronic Lymphocytic Leukaemia, Mantle Cell Lymphoma, or Waldenstrom's macroglobulinemia will experience AF during their treatment (Alexandre et al, 2018). We must highlight the fact that treatment with ibrutinib is usually for an indeterminate period. The relation between the newly emerging immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICI)- such as nivolumab, ipilimumab (melanoma), pembrolizumab, is still not well established. However, they may cause, atrioventricular block, myocarditis, ventricular arrhythmias, and even Takotsubo syndrome, pericarditis, and even thyroiditis and thyrotoxicosis which can induce AF (ESC, 2016). Regarding the proarrhythmic mechanisms involved, some of them are specific to the cancer treatment, such as ADP changes, calcium abnormalities, oxidative stress and mitochondrial dysfunction (anthracyclines), ischemia and electrolyte disturbances (cisplatin and 5FU), inhibition of cardiac PI3K- Akt signaling (ibrutinib) (Santhanakrishnan et al, 2016). Last but not least, when dealing with AF during cancer treatment, the clinician should always bear in mind that AF can be the evidence of a cardiovascular complication, such as new left ventricular dysfunction, acute myocarditis, acute pericarditis or pulmonary embolism or induced by electrolyte disturbances (hypokalemia, hypomagnesemia), anemia, bleeding and septic states. Therefore, newly onset AF must always be regarded as a warning sign, prompting the exclusion of the mentioned causes. In cases with no apparent cause for AF, clinicians should understand that there is a significant risk for LV systolic impairment and subsequent heart failure (ESC, 2016). Heart failure will occur in more than one-third of individuals with AF at some point (Larsen et al, 2014)

As in patients without cancer, the management of AF in cancer patients must address the issues of rhythm or rate control, thromboembolic prophylaxis, and effective stroke prevention with anticoagulation and bleeding risk (ESC, 2016). CHA₂DS₂-VASc and HAS-BLED risk scores have not been validated in patients with cancer since although malignancies induce a prothrombotic state, they may also predispose to bleeding (ESC, 2016). However, anticoagulation can be initiated in patients with CHA₂DS₂-VASc score ≥ 2 and a platelet count $> 50\ 000/\text{mm}^3$ (ESC, 2016). Figure 1

Anticoagulation agents include warfarin, LMWH for a short-intermediate time, or non-VKA oral anticoagulants (NOACs). Warfarin should be avoided in metastatic stages with LMWH being preferred (ESC, 2016). NOACs have been validated in cancer patients with VTE, but their

indication for stroke prevention in AF is to be established (ESC, 2016). However, some trials suggest that they are safe in patients with a platelet count $>100.000/\text{mm}^3$ (ASE et EACVI, 2014). The issue with NOACs is that many cancer therapeutics interact with CYP3A4 pathway metabolism and can alter their pharmacokinetics with risks of bleeding or thrombosis. Some clinicians prefer to use LMWH for 2 weeks to expose immediate bleeding risks and then transition to a NOAC, but caution is needed in GI malignancy (higher thrombotic risk), cerebral metastases (higher bleeding risk), and chemotherapy-induced thrombocytopenia (ESC, 2016). In the conundrum of rhythm control versus rate control, some comments have to be made. Firstly, supraventricular arrhythmias are usually poorly tolerated by these patients given the left ventricular impairment induced by cancer therapeutics. High ventricular rates are detrimental in patients receiving anthracyclines because they impair mitochondrial production of ATP. For example, a heart rate reduction of 10 beats/min can save almost 5kg of ATP allowing more energy to be used for contraction and relaxation (Lyon, 2019). Secondly, the loss of atrial contraction (which accounts for 25-30% of stroke-volume) can induce severe symptoms in these patients, altering their effort capacity and downgrading their ECOG Scale Performance Status. Rhythm control is of course ideal and should be managed by an experienced cardiologist. Some particular aspects are that amiodarone and sotalol should be avoided because they prolong QT (which can lead to malignant ventricular arrhythmias) and AF ablation can be considered after cancer treatment is completed (ESC, 2016). Clinicians are advised to begin with rate control using beta-blockers (calcium channel blockers have interactions with many cancer therapeutics and are not preferred) then assess the response (Lyon, 2019). If the heart rate is still not controlled, the patient should be referred to a specialist for cardioversion (electrical and/or pharmacologic), ablation, or in extreme cases, atrioventricular node ablation with permanent cardiac pacing to avoid tachycardia-induced cardiomyopathy (Lyon, 2019).

Screening and follow-up

Ideally, every cancer patient should have a baseline cardiac assessment (ESC, 2016) (ASE and EACVI, 2014). However, this is not always possible. Clinicians should select patients with a high risk for developing CTRCD, such as those patients with established or risk factors for cardiovascular disease, those with pre-existing LV systolic/diastolic impairment, those over 65 years, and those scheduled to receive high doses of type I agents ($>350\ \text{mg}/\text{m}^2$) or combined chemotherapy with both types I and type II agents (Galderisi et al, 2017). Three-dimensional echocardiography is the method of choice for monitoring LV function and detecting CTRCD and

GLS is the optimal parameter of deformation for the early detection of sub-clinical LV dysfunction, although cardiac magnetic resonance is the reference standard in the evaluation of LV and RV volumes and LVEF, especially in patients with suboptimal echocardiographic image (ASE and EACVI, 2014). The patient must be referred to a cardiologist when: the LVEF is <53%, GLS is abnormal and troponins are elevated (ASE and EACVI, 2014). In this case, the cardiologist and oncologist should discuss the risk/benefit ratio, bearing in mind that the cancer treatment is at the discretion of the oncologist. Follow-up is different based on the type of agent used. For type I agents in a dose <240mg/m², follow-up is recommended upon completion of therapy (ASE and EACVI, 2014). For doses >240mg/m², follow-up is indicated before each additional cycle. In the case of trastuzumab, follow-up is indicated every 3 months during therapy (ASE and EACVI, 2014). Since TKI, especially ibrutinib, have a high incidence of AF, patients receiving them should be screened systematically for AF using 3 to 7 days Holter monitoring, Apple watches, and ILR (internal loop recorders) (Galderisi et al, 2017) (ESC, 2016).

Dealing with cancer patients – our perspective

Our hospital is one of the biggest multidisciplinary hospitals in Bucharest, Romania. Patients from the Hematology, Oncology, and Internal Medicine departments are referred to our department for Cardiology consultations. Therefore, we have first-hand experience with cancer patients, which enables us to share some insight. We hope that our message, along with the current knowledge from the literature, will serve clinicians of all sorts to better understand the needs of this particular population. Firstly, patients with malignancies form a heterogeneous population in terms of age, comorbidities, and cardiovascular risk factors. We see patients with cancer of all ages who experience CTRCD and we are concerned that younger patients, who don't have any prior cardiovascular diseases or risk factors are not properly screened before or during their cancer treatment since they are considered clinically fit by default. Unfortunately, we see younger patients (<40 years) only when they experience a clinically manifesting cardiovascular complication, such as arterial hypertension, pericarditis, atrial fibrillation, or heart failure (usually with preserved ejection fraction). We cannot stress enough the importance of screening all cancer patients before their treatment, monitoring them closely during the treatment, and following up on them even after they completed the treatment. Because cancer patients usually have a complicated clinical course, following up on them is particularly difficult and more often than not, we see these patients only once. Furthermore, it is possible that they will not be followed by the same cardiologist, which is detrimental. Also, since GLS is

intervendor-variable, these patients must be monitored using the same ultrasound device. Another issue we would like to highlight is that after the treatment is completed, although these patients are closely monitored regarding their malignancy, they are paradoxically less evaluated for other comorbidities and long-term complications. For instance, we have a cohort of cancer survivors with heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF) who had insidious heart failure symptoms (such as occasional dyspnea with ordinary or more than ordinary physical activity, paroxysmal nocturnal dyspnea and discrete, but constant peripheral edema) for 3 to 18 months before they were seen by a cardiologist, properly diagnosed and treated accordingly. Typically, these patients have other comorbidities, are used to lower than normal quality of life, and rarely involve in more than ordinary physical activities. Besides, we observed that non-cardiology specialists who see these patients do not properly screen them for typical symptoms of heart failure by asking simple and focused questions, such as: *Have you experienced any limitation with ordinary physical activity? How would you describe your ordinary physical activities? Have you noticed swelling of your lower limbs before bedtime? Did you wake up in the middle of the night with shortness of breath?* Although simple and common, we encourage clinicians to ask cancer survivors these questions to identify heart failure symptoms and refer them to a cardiologist promptly. Taking into consideration the volume of cancer patients who would benefit from our Cardiology follow-up care, we are exploring the possibility of establishing a dedicated Cardio-Oncology service. Furthermore, we are promoting the idea of the cardiologist as a member of the tumor board for patients with cardiovascular diseases or at great risk of developing one. All in all, the role of the cardiologist in the clinical outcome of cancer patients is just shaping up. We must always bear in mind that ultimately, the oncologist has the final say and draws the conclusion. In some cases, developing a cardiovascular complication is just the price that cancer patients have to pay to survive. Therefore, caution is advised when recommending against certain drug regimens or when deeming patients cardiologically unfit for treatment, since the stakes are very high for in this case.

CONCLUSION

As discussed, the interplay between the patient's pre-existing cardiovascular risk and cancer therapeutics is complex, but progress has been made in understanding how cancer treatment affects the heart and vasculature during and after treatment and how clinicians can lend their support. Cardio-Oncology will have to answer more questions in the future and attend to the needs of an increasing population of cancer survivors, while also

establishing suitable cardiovascular therapies for patients undergoing treatment. Probably of utmost concern is that cancer patients are seen by a cardiologist too late, for instance when they have heart failure symptoms. It becomes imperative for internists and oncologists to understand the chain of cardiovascular complications and their meaning in these patients and carefully select the patients for screening and follow-ups. Last but not least, some complications, such as AF, can be easily managed by internists and should not be overlooked or underestimated because treating them and their underlying cause could make a difference for the patient. Ultimately, bridging these two distinct medical fields will be possible through the training of dedicated specialists.

Take-home messages

- Cancer patients will experience many different complications, as previously described, during or after treatment. Chances are they will be seen by internists, who will have to think of the cardiovascular risk of these patients and select those with subclinical forms of CTRCD and refer them to a cardiologist, bearing in mind the following triad: symptoms, biomarkers, and imaging (ultrasound) parameters.
- Internists should always be aware that cancer patients and survivors are an at-risk population in terms of cardiovascular diseases and should treat them accordingly.
- Atrial fibrillation is always a warning sign in these patients and not an innocent bystander.
- CTRCD does not mean only anthracyclines. It extends to trastuzumab, TKI, ICI, and becomes more relevant with higher cancer survival rates. Moreover, the list of antineoplastic drugs with cardiac side effects is updated permanently.
- Patients with chronic malignancies receiving treatment over an indefinite time should be routinely screened for AF and left ventricular function.
- Cardiologists should assess all patients before receiving cancer therapy especially those with risk factors. Oncologists and cardiologists should discuss cases in which the benefit/risk ratio becomes uncertain. Ultimately, the oncologist decides the course of the treatment. The cardiologist treats the patients to help them complete their cancer treatment and avoid cardiac side-effects.
- In the attempt to offer cancer patients and survivors the best support and therapeutical conduct, internists are the missing link and could make a difference if made aware of their particularities.

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